

Cathodic protection of tin-coated steel in monochloroacetic acid (0.5 mol dm^{-3}) in presence of chromates and dichromates

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Abstract : Potentiostatic weight loss technique has been used to study cathodic protection of steel coated with tin in 0.5 mol dm^{-3} monochloroacetic acid in presence of alkali metal chromates and dichromates. For complete protection 0.1296 amp/dm^2 current is required. The conjoint effect of cathodic current and inhibitors is antagonistic. High polarization and low current density for film formation may be a cause for protection.

Keywords : Chromates, steel, monochloroacetic acid, dichromates, cathodic protection.

Introduction

Corrosion of metals is a major industrial problem and has attracted investigators world wide¹. The application of corrosion inhibitors in closed system is one of the major protective method. In this note, we have described protection of tin coated steel in presence of chromates and dichromates.

Experimental

Tata tinplate (0.21 mm thick) (Jamshedpur) has been used in the present work. Chemical composition of base steel is (mg/sq.m) chromium 3.5–6.5, carbon 0.5–1.0 and molybdenum 3.5–6.5. All chemicals used were AnalaR grade, quality and purity was checked by standard methods. Solutions were prepared in conductivity water and strengths were measured by standard procedures².

For cathodic protection studies, the metal coupon was of circular design (2.8 cm diameter with $3 \times 0.5 \text{ cm}$ long handle) and washed with water, alcohol, and acetone and ultimately dried in air. The whole set of coupon and electrode was coated with wax leaving only the circular portion with an apparent surface area of tin coated sheet exposed to the corrosive medium.

H-type Pyrex glass cell with two compartments separated by a porous partition was used in this work. A built in capillary to make connections with the reference satu-

rated calomel electrode was also attached with it. Volume of corrosive media was 80 ml in each compartment at $35 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The electrochemical cell used for the study was a three electrode system with a working, a second as reference (SCE) and a third one as a counter electrode. In the present study distilled water was used to remove corrosion products.

Results and discussion

Under the influence of external cathodic polarization the effectiveness of the inhibitor may change towards the negative or a positive effect. This may be due to change in the adsorption characteristics of an inhibitor under the influence of an external cathodic polarization (Fig. 1). As the cathodic current density increases, loss in weight due to corrosion decreases. The current density required for complete protection was dependent on the inhibitor and its concentration (Table 1), weight loss results are given in Table 2.

The conjoint effect is antagonistic (less negative) for all inhibitors and it is higher at lower current densities. At higher current density, the adsorption characteristics of inhibitor get changed under the influence of applied current. Inhibitors reduce the current required for cathodic protection (Table 3). Without inhibitor, the steel is protected at -0.529 mV cathode potential (SCE). The

Fig. 1. Effect of varying current density on the cathode and anode potential of tin coated steel in 0.5 M monochloroacetic acid in the presence of potassium chromate and potassium dichromate (■) 0.5% chromate cathodic, (●) 0.5% chromate anodic, (▲) 1.0% chromate cathodic, (▼) 1.0% chromate anodic, (◆) 0.5% dichromate cathodic, (◀) 0.5% dichromate anodic, (▶) 1.0% dichromate cathodic, (◉) 1.0% dichromate anodic

protection potential does not remain the same and changes with concentration of inhibitor. It is negative (-329 mV) in presence of 5% $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

A combination of cathodic protection and an inhibitor which is adsorbed at negative potentials may give greater protection than either system alone³. It was suggested that lower current density is required for cathodic protection in inhibited rather than un-inhibited solutions⁴

On reduction $CH_2Cl.COOH$ liberates HCl. The dissolution of coated steel in acid solution is generally accompanied by the liberation of hydrogen. These reactions may occur at the micro electrodes of the corrosion cell. Tin should be cathodic to iron but the potential reverses in most sealed cans and the tin acts as a sacrificial coating, thus protecting the steel. Tin is relatively inert but in presence of oxygen or other oxidizing agents it is attacked.

Chromates and dichromates are very good passivators. Passivators are oxidizing agents with redox potentials that

Table 1. Effect of current density on cathodic weight loss of tin coated steel in 0.5 M monochloroacetic acid (cathodic protection)

Inhibitor name (Concentration)	Period of immersion 15 min, temperature $35 \pm 0.1^\circ C$		Protection % due to Current I_1	Potential		mV (SCE)
	Current density (amp/dm ²)	Weight loss (mg/dm ²)		Current + Inhibitor I_{obs}		
Nil	0	56.74	-	-	-	-463
	0.0162	43.77	23	-	-	-507
	0.0324	34.04	40	-	-	-511
	0.0486	24.32	57	-	-	-513
	0.0648	16.21	71	-	-	-515
	0.0972	9.73	83	-	-	-523
	0.1296	0.00	100	-	-	-529
Potassium chromate (0.5%)	0	40.53	-	29	-	-115
	0.0162	17.83	51	69	-	-149
	0.0324	8.11	80	86	-	-306
	0.0648	0.00	100	100	-	-410
Potassium chromate (1%)	0	29.18	-	49	-	-85
	0.0162	17.83	39	69	-	-154
	0.0324	6.48	78	89	-	-180
	0.0486	0.00	100	100	-	-259
Sodium chromate (0.5%)	0	12.97	-	77	-	-191
	0.0162	4.86	63	91	-	-219
	0.0324	3.57	73	94	-	-334
	0.0648	0.00	100	100	-	-405
Sodium chromate (1%)	0	8.11	-	86	-	-24
	0.0162	4.86	40	86	-	-95

Note

Table-1 (contd)

	0.0324	2.92	64	95	-225
	0.0486	0.00	100	100	-350
Potassium dichromate (0.5%)	0	12.97	-	77	-137
	0.0162	4.86	63	91	-140
	0.0324	3.24	75	94	-150
	0.0648	0.00	100	100	-329
Potassium dichromate (1%)	0	8.11	-	86	70
	0.0162	6.48	2.0	89	56
	0.0324	3.24	60	94	50
	0.0486	0.00	100	100	-39
Sodium dichromate (0.5%)	0	18.11	68		-92
	0.0162	10.21	44	82	-140
	0.0324	4.86	73	91	-217
	0.0648	0.00	100	100	-341
Sodium dichromate (1%)	0	12.80	-	77	48
	0.0162	9.73	24	83	-120
	0.0324	4.86	62	91	-130
	0.0486	0.00	100	100	-167
Ammonium dichromate (0.5%)	0	17.83	-	69	-61
	0.0162	14.59	18	74	-96
	0.0324	6.48	64	89	-140
	0.0648	0.00	100	100	-321
Ammonium dichromate (1%)	0	14.65	-	74	83
	0.0162	8.15	44	86	43
	0.0324	4.86	67	91	14
	0.0486	0.00	100	100	-77

Table 2. Weight loss in the absence and presence of protective current, efficiencies of inhibitors and ratio of i_p and i_t in 0.5 M monochloroacetic acid for tin coated steel

Inhibitor (Concentration)	Without external cathodic current			With external cathodic current		
	Weight loss (mg/dm ²)	Inhibitor efficiency (%)	Theoretical current for complete protection (i_t) (amp/dm ²)	Current for complete protection (i_p) (amp/dm ²)	% Reduction in current due to inhibitor	Ratio (i_p/i_t)
Nil	56.74	-	0.1946	0.1296	-	0.67
Potassium chromate (0.5%)	40.53	29	0.1390	0.0648	50	0.47
Potassium chromate (1%)	29.18	49	0.1001	0.0486	62.5	0.49
Sodium chromate (0.5%)	12.97	77	0.0445	0.0648	50	1.46
Sodium chromate (1%)	8.11	86	0.0278	0.0486	62.5	1.75
Potassium dichromate (0.5%)	12.97	77	0.0445	0.0648	50	1.46
Potassium dichromate (1%)	8.11	86	0.0278	0.0486	62.5	1.75
Sodium dichromate (0.5%)	18.11	68	0.0621	0.0648	50	1.04
Sodium dichromate (1%)	12.8	77	0.0439	0.0486	62.5	1.11
Ammonium dichromate (0.5%)	17.83	69	0.0611	0.0648	50	1.06
Ammonium dichromate (1%)	14.65	74	0.0502	0.0486	62.5	0.97

Table 3. Effect of cathodic polarization on performance of different inhibitors in 0.5 M monochloroacetic acid

Inhibitor (Concentration)	Weight loss (mg/dm ²)	Order of inhibitor action as per loss in weight	Current required for complete protection (Amp/dm ²)	Order of inhibitor action as per current required	Protective corrosion potential mV (SCE)
0.5 M Monochloroacetic acid	56.74	-	0.1296	-	-529
Potassium chromate (0.5%)	40.53	7	0.0648	2	-410
Potassium chromate (1%)	29.18	6	0.0486	1	-259
Sodium dichromate (0.5%)	18.11	5	0.0648	2	-341
Ammonium dichromate (0.5%)	17.83	4	0.0648	2	-321
Ammonium dichromate (1%)	14.65	3	0.0486	1	-77
Potassium dichromate (0.5%)	12.97	2	0.0648	2	-329
Sodium chromate (0.5%)	12.97	2	0.0648	2	-405
Sodium dichromate (1%)	12.80	2	0.0486	1	-167
Potassium dichromate (1%)	8.11	1	0.0486	1	-39
Sodium chromate (1%)	8.11	1	0.0486	1	-350

are higher than the metals and are readily reduced. Passivating agents are reduced at cathodic area. As passivation gets established on the metal surface, passive areas became noble to adjacent areas and passivity spreads over the entire metal surface. Once passivity of the entire metal surface is achieved, the whole surface function as a cathode and further reduction of the passivator is very slow and only a small current flows. For the optimum inhibitor corrosion concentration must be greater than a critical concentration. If inhibitor lies below the critical level, incomplete passivation is found and the passivator can function as an active depolarizer at other (unpassivated) areas such that increased corrosion rate are observed in localized areas and pitting occurs.

Conclusion

Dichromates and chromates are passivator type of

corrosion inhibitors and reduce cathodic areas at a current density equivalent to that at anodic areas. It is greater than critical current density of metal.

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